

THE USEFULNESS OF FEEDBACK FOR THE TEACHER**Polumeeva I.***Saint-Petersburg University of Management Technologies and Economics*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8091861>**Abstract**

The article by Polumeeva I.N. considers the issue of the benefits of feedback for the teacher, which has a positive impact on both the teaching process and the learning process, indicates the need for feedback not only to monitor the assimilation of educational material, but also to understand the perception and expectations of the audience and create an effective learning environment, draws attention to understanding the feedback from the student's position.

Keywords: feedback, usefulness of feedback, personification of learning, effective learning environment, personal contact.

The learning process in modern conditions increasingly combines techniques of online and offline format. Being in a real classroom and speaking to an audience of listeners, the teacher can see the interest of students in the topic being presented, notice by the reaction to the questions posed who does not understand the answer to this or that question, whether students hear or listen to the teacher, change the sequence of presentation of the material and switch to interactive methods. With distance learning, these visual indicators are absent and feedback can be obtained by contacting the listeners directly. Is feedback important for the teacher? Teachers of domestic universities have a high annual workload – classroom and extracurricular, and the calculation of extracurricular workload does not take into account work with students on feedback, and these are responses to messages in messengers, and e-mail, and a learning portal, checking additional tasks in addition to tasks for monitoring the assimilation of educational additional tasks besides the tasks for monitoring the assimilation of educational material. Won't it be a waste of time for out-of-class or out-of-lecture communication with the audience? The conducted research in foreign and domestic pedagogical practice indicates the need and importance of feedback for both the teacher and the student.

In the modern glossary of a teacher, feedback is the transfer of information between participants in the pedagogical process, it is the causal determination of the actions of each of them. [1] Feedback is established to improve the effectiveness of learning. Good feedback practice encourages teacher-student dialogue, provides teachers with information that can be used to form a teaching system. [2, 201-205] Feedback can be positive or negative, both for the teacher and for the student. From the student's point of view, a high score, a laudatory review or comment, not ignoring messages, comments on corrected errors, recommendations for an additional source of information, a wish for a speedy recovery (for example, if a student wrote in a message to

the teacher that he was ill and could not come to class), all this is a positive feedback. Positive feedback for the teacher is a high score of passing the exam, correct answers in the classroom, activity, the desire of listeners to answer questions and ask questions on the topic being studied, the gratitude of the student for an interesting lesson, course, for professionalism, expressing wishes for the organization of the educational process. A negative feedback reaction also takes place, and it can cause negative emotions in both the teacher and the student. For example, this is not a certification in a subject, a delay in responding to a message, a missed deadline (delivery and verification of a task), etc., and the same of the listed topics causes negative emotions on both sides of the participants in the educational process. The failure of the student's exam did not bring joy or satisfaction to the teacher. The student's desire to tell the teacher about the reasons for his failure and the teacher's desire to listen to the student, the presence of a dialogue, is the key to good partnerships. The establishment of contact between the teacher and the student, as the main participants in the educational process, also contributes to the personification of learning. Personalized, that is, a personality-oriented learning process that allows you to constantly monitor current changes in students. Searches for and updates the personal resources of each subject of the educational process. [3, 127-128]

The first- and second-year students of my groups were asked to take a feedback survey. Figure 1 shows the percentage of all responses. To the question whether feedback from the teacher is important, 97% of respondents answered in the affirmative, and whether feedback is important for the teacher – 94% believe that it is important. Among the means of feedback, the information and educational portal of the university was most often called (67%), messengers (WhatsApp, Telegram) were in second place (23%) and in third with 10% -email.

Figure 1. Means of feedback.

It is important to note that in order to find out the information of interest on the subject, 97% wrote that they turned directly to the teacher, and not to the tutor. According to the first-year students, feedback is needed in order to find out the results of checking completed tasks and clarify the deadlines, these provided answers were chosen, as shown in Figure 2, by the same number of respondents (43% each) and only a small part of the first-year students who participated in the survey, 14 percent gave their own answer. They believe that feedback is needed to be able to ask individual questions, receive additional assignments and make progress on the subject. That is, the usefulness of feedback for a student in an effort to get more scores on the subject. Second-year students in most cases gave their answers. In

their opinion, feedback is needed to ensure mutual understanding and correct communication, and it can also help the teacher better understand the expectations of students, it is possible to adjust the course at the beginning of training for better assimilation of knowledge by students, and not ask at the end of the course what difficulties they encountered in the learning process. Second-year students in most cases gave their answers. In their opinion, feedback is needed to ensure mutual understanding and correct communication, and it can also help the teacher better understand the expectations of students, it is possible to adjust the course at the beginning of training for better assimilation of knowledge by students, and not ask at the end of the course what difficulties they encountered in the learning process.

Figure 2. Purpose of feedback according to first-year- students.

Conclusion

The main participants in the learning process are faced with new tasks both in teaching the discipline and in mastering it, an effective solution to these tasks is possible with constant feedback for the teacher to understand their students' capabilities and expectations at certain stages of learning.

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APPLICATION OF INNOVATIVE TEACHING TECHNOLOGIES**Sakipova Sh.**

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Analyzing the experience of introducing innovative teaching technologies in universities, the following main directions of their application:

-preparation of educational materials, first of all electronic textbooks, for independent work of students and classroom activities;

- use of computer technology as a means of teaching and control in the educational process of the university;

-development databases on academic disciplines, etc.

Students are offered training materials, made in the form of electronic textbooks, many of which textbooks duplicate educational information from paper carriers, without using the extensive computer capabilities.

The electronic textbook is a comprehensive educational software system providing continuity and completeness of the didactic cycle: the provision of theoretical material, the organization of training and information retrieval activities, the control of the level of knowledge, the implementation of interactive feedback.

Two technologies for the development of an electronic textbook have become widespread: a technology based on the concept of typical screens: a screen saver, registration, an information screen, a screen of questions, an exercise screen [1]; technology, based on the use of the method of theoretical images, as a visual-figurative representation of the semantics of verbalized forms of scientific knowledge: concepts, laws, theories. The first technology does not provide a holistic perception of educational information by students because of its fragmentary presentation. This shortcoming is overcome by applying the method of theoretical images, which allows to develop and generalize the necessary information as the student requests.

Along with electronic textbooks that reproduce a full didactic cycle, software systems are applied that cover individual fragments of the didactic cycle: informational, encyclopedic and examining electronic books.

Encyclopedic e-books contain a large amount of information on a certain topic, presented in the form of articles arranged on a thematic principle.

Information e-books contain not so extensive information, but it is more focused, they are usually used in the real learning process as an additional reference tool.

Examination e-books contain a block of questions-tasks, a testing module and an expert system for analyzing and evaluating answers.

The improvement of electronic textbooks should be based on the use of modern technologies such as multimedia: a multivariate environment, "virtual reality", etc., which can be successfully applied not only in the implementation of the self - study Students, but also in the audience.

Multimedia - a technology that provides work with video, animation, text and sound. Information obtained with digital cameras, scanners, camcorders and other external sources, after appropriate processing and, possibly, with the addition of text, animation and special effects, is recorded in a multimedia file.

The use of multimedia in the learning process ensures the effective flow of perceptive-mnemonic processes due to the optimal interaction of visual and audio effects.

In combination with hypertext, it forms hypermedia: super complex, based on the method of discrete representation of information on nodes, linked by reference.

Despite the complexity of developing and implementing in the educational process - the high cost of hardware and software, the new computer technology, the "virtual reality", is creating an illusion of direct presence in the stereoscopically presented "screen world".

Its introduction into the educational process allows modeling various types of activities of the future specialist, especially if it is necessary to work out a system of actions in emergency production situations.

The physics "virtual laboratory works" are successfully applied in physics, which in combination with bench works have a great cognitive value and allow students to perform all necessary measurements, record